

Supplementary Information

Antibacterial activity and evaluation of the kinetic release of *Laureliopsis philippiana* (Looser) essential oil from nanostructured porous silicon with surface-functionalization alternatives

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S1. Antibacterial evaluation

The microorganisms were activated in LB medium for 3 hours at 37 °C. Then, the amounts indicated in Table S1 were added for the *L. philippiana* essential oil and the mineral oil, respectively. Only LB media was used as a control. The strains were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h without agitation. Finally, 250 µL were recovered at an OD 600 nm in 96-well plates.

Table S1. Incubation protocol for the antibacterial evaluation of *L. philippiana* essential oil and mineral oil.

Microorganism culture (µL)	LB medium (µL)	Essential oil (µL)	Microorganism culture (µL)	LB medium (µL)	Mineral oil (µL)
5	295	150	5	295	150
5	295	120	5	295	120
5	295	90	5	295	90
5	295	60	5	295	60
5	295	30	5	295	30
5	295	0	5	295	0
5	295	0	5	295	0
5	295	0	5	295	0

S2. Antibacterial activity

The reproducibility of the antimicrobial effect of *L. philippiana* essential oil was determined using an extract obtained in 2021 compared to a sample from a three-year-old. The viability percentage was analyzed in the *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* strains (Figure S1).

Figure S1. Comparison of bacterial growth inhibition of essential oil in different years. The effect of different volume/volume ratio of essential oil (solid line) and three-year-old essential oil (segmented line) was evaluated using (A) *Staphylococcus aureus* and (B) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The essential oil three-year-old result was from 1 independent experiment (n=1).